

Transparency Policy

14 June 2023: Approved by Board of Trustees

Purpose of this policy

This policy defines transparency, a core principle of the OA Book Usage Data Trust. It aims to set expectations for information sharing as it applies to the vision, mission and operations of the Trust, its staff, Trustees and committee members. The policy codifies a culture of openness meant to engender trust and accountability within the Trust and with its diverse external stakeholders. This policy does not cover the data in the data exchange itself. It should be read in concert with the Data Rule Book and Operations Manual as available.

Transparency Definition

For the purposes of this policy, transparency means the Data Trust operates “As open as possible, as closed as necessary.” Transparency means information is provided, in context, and in an open and timely manner so that stakeholders can audit and trust operations, governance and data processing approaches of the OA Book Usage Data Trust.

Availability and Access to Information

In order to ensure that the Data Trust responsibly operates as open as possible, as closed as necessary, information generally falls into one of two levels of access:

1. Openly available, generally on or linked to from the website or published
2. Restricted access, i.e. for internal operations

At times, some information may be determined to be excessive, impractical and/or sensitive and delayed, restricted or made available on an as-needed basis.

Open information is made public, online, in a timely manner as resources allow. Information that may change over time, including policies like this one, are versioned and dated.

Restricted access refers to role-based access to materials which may contain information that may be bound by contractual or other agreements that preclude open sharing. “Restricted” is not equivalent to “confidential” as the Trust is subject to public information requirements due to its organizational context.

The provision of information covered by this policy is maintained by OA Book Usage Data Trust staff in combination with the Secretary of the Board.